

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers:

The September issue of J.UCS consists of three papers that have mainly a theoretical flavor. Thus it is appropriate to solicit also, once more, more applied papers: help to spread the information that J.UCS is a medium suitable for all kinds of computer science papers: research and survey, broad or narrow.

It is the last point that I have to particularly emphasize: I have heard a number of times statements to the extent "this is a good paper for a specialized journal, but not for J.UCS". Such statements show a misunderstanding of the aims of J.UCS: J.UCS is NOT intended for just "general" papers that would not fit some specialized journal: it is intended as a kind of union of all possible journals in computer science....hence the title "universal". By selecting a special category a "specialized journal" can be obtained!

Happy reading, and don't forget to submit papers and encourage colleagues to read J.UCS.

Cordially

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PS: The printed version of volume 1 of J.UCS will appear in February 1996. Since it will be an exact copy of the PostScript form of the electronic version of J.UCS authors can quote their papers, complete with page numbers, already in the correct form in 1995, despite the fact that the printed version will appear in 1996.